

PHYTONYMS USED IN FOLKLORE

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Abstract. This article talks about the phytonymic names used in folklore and their specific features. It should be noted that the phytonym units used in folklore are used based on the life of the people and they have their own reasons. In this article, which we want to study, we will talk about the use of phytonymic names in folklore.

Keywords: folklore, phytonymic names, phytonymic units, causes of origin.

Today, at a time when the field of linguistics is developing more and more, the field of its study is also expanding, and the database is divided into wide networks. It should be noted that linguistics has now entered all areas of our life. In particular, psychology, mathematics, computer science, biology, etc., have become direct objects of study in the field of language. At this point, it is natural to ask a question, how can sciences not related to linguistics develop in direct connection with the direction of language? It is worth noting that the subjects whose names are recorded can become the research object of linguistics with the terms, names, and units present in them [4]. In this article, which we want to analyze, as the subject of our research, the phytonymic units, which are the names of plants, were revealed closely with the biological sciences, and their interrelationship with folklore was highlighted in cooperation with the field of literature.

Folk oral works are literary samples that have been passed down from mouth to mouth for centuries, and they are divided into certain groups, namely, lyrical, epic, dramatic and special type. A number of phytonymic names are used for each of the above-mentioned species. Phytonyms are the names given to plants, and the names in them originate for three different reasons. First, the person who found the name of the plant acts as a name for phytonymic units, and the names invented by the

people are also names for phytonyms. serves as Thirdly, the appearance of the plant plays a key role in the emergence of their names [7].

The reasons for the naming of plant names (Fig. 1).

In the poetic genres of the lyrical type of folklore, the names of plants are mainly named according to their appearance. Consider the passage below:

Guli sapsarni ko`ring,

Suvga qarab qayriladi.

Bevafo yorni ko`ring,

O`lmay turib ayriladi[13].

The phytonymic unit used in the above passage is "guli sapsar", and its form "**gulsapsar**" is also often used in our speech. In the "Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" this lexeme is defined as follows: "A perennial plant with leaves, white, pink, blue, purple or yellow flowers and its flower." If we dwell on the etymology of the word, this word was formed from the combination of the lexeme "sapsar" which means "purple perennial plant" with the base "flower" (**gul+sapsar**). Therefore, the unique appearance of this flower served as the basis for the formation of this phytonymic name [13].

Pay attention to the following excerpt from the folklore "*Osmondagi yulduzni*":

Uyim oldi katta bog`,

Rayhon ekoman deyman.

*Yorimga sovg`a qilib,
Do`ppi tikoman deyman[13].*

The phytonymic unit used in the mentioned passage is the lexeme "basil". This word is the Turkish version of the Arabic word "basil". This unit is also used in Dari, Iranian-Persian, and Tajik languages in the form of "rayhan". In the Turkmen language, its variant "reyhan" is popular [8].

Another lyrical song popular in folklore is the song "Boychechak":

*Boychechagim boylandi,
Qozon to`la ayron di.
Ayroningdan bermasang,
Qozonlaring vayron dir[13].*

The lexeme "boychechak" used in the above poetic passage is used as a phytonymic name. There are different opinions about the use of this phytonym unit in lyric poetry, and in some of them, this name indicates that it is divine, in others, it is expressed in the meaning of the arrival of light, the beginning of goodness. Based on scientific sources, we can explain the etymology of the word as follows: "rich" - god; "smallpox" - flower, i.e., "flower of God", this syntactic unit, which expresses the dictionary meaning, in the vernacular, is used in the above-mentioned poetic passage as a reference to the degree to which that year will come. In addition, it figuratively reflects the expression of the end of the winter season, the beginning of spring, the beginning of greenery, stepping into the light. So, we can say that some names used in folklore are significant because they mean deep meaning.

As a conclusion, we can say that the phytonymic units used in folklore are related to the family of plants, mainly flowers, in which the main attention is paid to the appearance, color, color and characteristics of flowers. In addition, there are also figurative names given by the people, which are significant because they indicate the different conditions of the people's lifestyle. Identifying them and expressing an opinion on this matter serves as the main research object of linguistics in the study of phytonymic names [9].

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